

Deliverable 1.8

ObsSea4Clim Project Website

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DELIVERABLE

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Deliverable Lead	Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut (DMI)
Author	Irene Robles Garcia (DMI)
Reviewers	Chiara Bearzotti (DMI), Erika Hayashi (DMI)

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1 Publishable summary

This deliverable aims to present the first version of the ObsSea4Clim project website, which was launched on 21 February 2024. The website is a key communication and dissemination tool for the project. It will be used as a resource to share information about the project's aims, and its partners, to update on the status of work and to share the project results, across a large variety of stakeholders, including the European Commission's (EC) services. The ObsSea4Clim website can be accessed at: www.obssea4clim.eu The website has been designed and developed by the Project Office (PO) at the Coordinator organisation, the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI).

2 Objectives

2.1 Aim

The ObsSea4Clim website is a central point of reference for the project. It is designed with the main goal of highlighting the project's objectives, structure, partners, results and resources through a variety of media, using a cohesive visual identity and a user-friendly flow of information.

2.2 Audiences

The website has been designed to provide information about ObsSea4Clim to a wide range of target audiences:

- **Research and academic community:** in addition to general information about the project, the website provides links to access all academic peer-reviewed publications of the project, details of conferences where the project has been or will be presented, poster and video presentations and downloadable reports. This will allow scientists across the climate and ocean science communities to easily find and access results from the project.
- **Stakeholders:** information relevant to a wide range of stakeholders is provided through the Resources web page (reports and communication materials),

Publications and the News & Events page, which highlight where project partners will be active, encouraging synergies and in-person meetings. The Networks page presents the international frameworks and related projects with which ObsSea4Clim has strong ties.

- **Policymakers:** Several materials linked to the upcoming ObsSea4Clim's policy briefings will be made available through the project website, and related events will be showcased to increase uptake and participation.

3 Website preparation

3.1 Registration of website domain and hosting

The ObsSea4Clim website domain was registered on 7 February 2024 by the project coordinator, DMI. The domain is www.obssea4clim.eu, chosen so the project website would be easily identifiable and searchable using only the project acronym.

The ObsSea4Clim website is developed using Wordpress. This option was selected as the most effective in providing a website easy to design, manage and update by the DMI Project Office team, while at the same time providing a wide range of designs, being user-friendly and intuitive, and a cost-efficient choice.

The first version of the website was launched on 21 February 2024.

3.2 Accessibility

In the choice of the colour palette and of the structure of the website, we follow the guidelines of the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) international standard (<https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/>), ensuring that the webpages are perceivable, operable, understandable and robust.

3.3 Website structure

The following diagram and descriptions show the website structure as of April 2024, when this deliverable has been submitted. Nevertheless, this structure will be

continuously revised and updated when needed, to highlight new information, expand current sections or create new ones, and overall provide the user with a clear way to easily find all project resources.

Figure 1 ObsSea4Clim website structure (April 2024)

The paragraphs below provide a short description of the goal of each project web page together with a screenshot of their current design.

3.3.1 Home

The website home page provides a snapshot of the project, as an informative first impression for online stakeholders, designed to catch viewers' attention and encourage them to seek more information about the project. As such, the home page summarises the project, objectives, key figures, news and partners in a concise way and is in line with the project's visual identity. In-built links direct the user to the website pages giving more information about each topic.

Figure 2 ObsSea4Clim Homepage

Focus and Objectives

The overarching goal of ObsSea4Clim is to deliver an improved framework for nations' contributions to European ocean observations of EO/ECVs (Essential Ocean Variables/Essential Climate Variables) in support of regional and global climate assessments, projections and actionable indicators for sustainable development.

The objectives of ObsSea4Clim are:

- To develop and deliver new ocean indicators for sustainable development, provide improved EO/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing
- To advance the use of EO/ECVs for improved Earth System Models (ESM) and reduce uncertainty in climate projections
- To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs
- To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing
- To place Europe in the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus

[Learn about the building blocks of ObsSea4Clim](#)

Key numbers

4 years
February 2024 - January 2028

19 partners
From 13 countries

6 million euros
funding from the European Commission

6 ocean climate application areas

Recent news

[View all news →](#)

Monitoring the Ocean
Panel Discussion and Exhibition/Networking Event
13th April 2024, 15:00, Institut de Ciències del Mar (Barcelona)
Join us for our Satellite Event on Monitoring the Ocean

Join us on our Satellite Event 'Monitoring the Ocean' on 8 April

13th Mar 2024

Exploring Ocean-Climate Dynamics: Observations, Collaboration and Policy Implications at Ocean Best Practices

12th Feb 2024

13 – 14 March 2024, ObsSea4Clim Kick-off Meeting in Copenhagen

7th Feb 2024

Keep up to date with ObsSea4Clim

5th Feb 2024

Consortium Partners

ObsSea4Clim is a strong partnership that brings together the main European and international actors involved in ocean observation, ocean and climate, modelling and forecasting. It comprises national and international research institutions and organisations with excellent expertise in the Atlantic, Arctic and European seas, as well as on the global ocean and climate.

[Get to know the partners](#)

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Contact

Project Coordinator
Dr. Steffen Olsen
Danish Meteorological Institute

Contact: obssea4clim@gmail.com

Follow us

[Privacy policy](#)

Website footer

The website footer, shown above as part of the Homepage, is common to the whole website, and therefore shown in the same way on every page. The footer displays the funding acknowledgement, including the EU flag and the funding statement as indicated in the Grant Agreement. In addition, a contact headline provides a quick way to find the contact of the project coordinator and an email address to get in touch with the project. The social media icons direct users to the ObsSea4Clim LinkedIn and YouTube accounts. The Privacy Policy link directs the user to a dedicated page covering this (S3.2.8).

3.3.2 About

This page presents the main concept and approach of the project. It introduces the Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR) and how it is adopted by the project. After this, a schematic diagram presents the building blocks of the project, followed by separate text boxes providing a short description of each building block.

Figure 3 An excerpt of ObsSea4Clim About page

About

Approach

Ocean climate observations, to be *sustainable*, must be an integral part of a multipurpose and integrated ocean observing system. Physical ocean climate observations are needed to deliver information and products to operational services (for instance, weather services, warning systems etc). The provided information is the baseline for drafting ocean state and climate assessments. To be able to deliver ocean forecasts and early warnings, climate projections and assessments and protect ocean health and its benefits, it is vital to measure Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs). These variables form the basis of the Global Climate Indicators that contain key information for the most relevant areas of climate change.

ObsSea4Clim aims at delivering an improved framework for sustainable ocean observation.

Our approach is based on the methodology developed by the World Meteorological Organisation, the Rolling Review of Requirements (WMO RRR). This WMO RRR system aims at integrating national observations to create a global system. At the heart of the system is a global set of data requirements for observations. This set has been generated from a synthesis of nations' regional requirements. The requirements are validated against existing and emerging observing capabilities. A regular review of these requirements is need to check their adequacy.

ObsSea4Clim will implement the functioning of a sustainable and global ocean observation system for monitoring and predicting climate changes.

ObsSea4Clim will adopt four methodological steps (light blue boxes) and apply them to six application areas (in the center of the diagram).

Building blocks of ObsSea4Clim

Building block 1

ObsSea4Clim definition of the Essential Ocean Variables and Essential Climate Variables (EOV/ECV) Framework

ObsSea4Clim focuses on refining the current global EO/ECVs framework to address regional and national climate information needs. This framework will be refined and integrated within the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS). *In practice*, this integration includes the following activities:

- 1) setting up a global integration,
- 2) establishing best practices and standards,
- 3) implementing an automatic quality control for recent and historical data,
- 4) aligning observational data to EO/ECVs.

Once the integration is achieved, this will support climate assessments, projections, and actionable indicators useful for policymaking.

Building block 2

ObsSea4Clim definition of EO/ECV-based Ocean Climate Indicators

ObsSea4Clim focuses on:

- the regionalization of indicators,
- the refinement of the indicator methods which are already in use,
- the application of the indicators to different time scales (short-term and long-term).

There is a strong need to work on the dissemination of these indicators to support sustainable ocean management. For this reason, ObsSea4Clim works in close contact with several representatives of ocean and climate initiatives (Stakeholder Reference Group) and with its sister projects, which have been funded under the same Horizon Europe [call](#).

3.3.3 News & Events

News

The news section is regularly updated and provides short posts presenting the latest updates from the project: from event attendance, publications, meetings or new results.

Figure 4 ObsSea4Clim News page

ObsSea4Clim OCEAN OBSERVATIONS AND INDICATORS FOR CLIMATE AND ASSESSMENTS

About Partners News & events Publications Resources Networks Contact

News

We have kicked off!

Copenhagen, Denmark | 13 – 14 March 2024
Over two days, the ObsSea4Clim consortium gathered in Copenhagen and online, diving into discussions across the project partners. The...

[Read more](#)

21st Mar 2024

Join us on our Satellite Event 'Monitoring the Ocean' on 8 April

Panel Discussion and Exhibition/Networking Event

Join ObsSea4Clim on 8 April 2024, at the Satellite Event to the Ocean Decade Conference 2024 in Barcelona. This Satellite Event "Monitoring the Ocean" will...

[Read more](#)

13th Mar 2024

Exploring Ocean-Climate Dynamics: Observations, Collaboration and Policy Implications at Ocean Best Practices

In October 2023, ObsSea4Clim project members, Sabrina Speich (ENS), Chiara Bearzotti (DMI), Gerard McCarthy (NUIM) and Ana Oliveira (+ATLANTIC) joined forces on a focus session...

[Read more](#)

Events

The event page provides a link to future and past events involving ObsSea4Clim. Each event is linked to a news post or the official event page providing more information about the agenda and role of the project.

3.3.4 Publications

Scientific publications

A link to the project's Zenodo community is provided. In addition, all peer-reviewed scientific publications published by ObsSea4Clim will be linked on this page.

Public deliverables

Once approved by the European Commission, all public deliverables will be made available on this page. For the time being a full list of the deliverables is available.

3.3.5 Resources

ObsSea4Clim will create several communication and dissemination materials, such as factsheets, press releases, newsletters, recommendations, and reports. These will be made available by linking resources published on Zenodo, the long-term repository of the project. For the time being, this section of the website is more of a “collector” of information. This area will be re-designed at a later stage when the project can provide more information and results.

3.3.6 Networks

The ObsSea4Clim project leverages collaborations with international frameworks, other projects and initiatives, and a large number of stakeholders which have been identified in the original proposal and refined during the kickoff meeting. The name and link to the webpage of these organisations or initiatives are collected under the Networks page. This page will be updated and expanded as needed to highlight key synergies and collaborations which are represented in the project’s Stakeholder Reference Group.

3.3.7 Contact

The Contact page provides the email addresses of the two main contacts of the coordination team. This information can also be found in the website footer.

Figure 9 ObsSea4Clim Contact page

3.3.8 Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy

The website’s Privacy Policy is described in detail, including the treatment of data collected through the website and the Cookie Policy. An email address for the responsible contact for data privacy at the Coordinator organization is also included.

4 Planned developments

The ObsSea4Clim project website will be continuously updated and improved to ensure an engaging, visual, accessible and user-friendly page. The following ideas will be incorporated into the website in the upcoming months:

- Review and update current graphics to better fit the ObsSea4Clim visual identity. If and when relevant, additional infographics will also be generated.
- Additional explanations, links and informative diagrams on key terminology and concepts of the project, including but not limited to: the Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR), Essential Ocean Variables (EOV), and the Essential Climate Variables (ECV).
- Specific content on user-friendly sections to facilitate the broader understanding of a non-specialist audience (general public).
- ObsSea4Clim application areas: a new section will be added to better present each of the project application areas: sea-ice loss, ocean transport, ocean stratification, sea level, marine heat waves, and ocean mesoscale. This will be done once activities in WP4 are more advanced, and will include geographical maps and highlights from the relevant tasks in WP4.
- Video materials: the website already provides the link to the ObsSea4Clim YouTube channel, where videos of presentations, and other short videos to support the dissemination and educational activities will be added. A selection of these will be highlighted on the website as embedded videos.

5 Website monitoring

As part of the overall monitoring of communication and dissemination activities, which includes the follow-up of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), website metrics will be regularly monitored. As a guideline, ObsSea4Clim set the KPI of receiving over 200 visits per month. The DMI Project Office will collect data/analytics on:

- number of visitors
- unique visitors

- distribution of visitors per page

global reach (the country from which visits are done).

This information will be analysed every three months and will be included in the communication and dissemination reports, such as deliverables (D1.2, D1.7) and official periodic reports to the European Commission (M18, M36, M48). The data will be used to analyse the reach and impact of the website, identify gaps in the project reach, deduce if specific content is particularly effective, and reshape the website strategy or improve content as required.

6 Post-project website management

The project website will be maintained for at least 5 years after the project's end by the project coordinator, DMI. After the project's end, the website and its content will remain under the DMI infrastructure, with the domain name maintained by DMI, potentially as a sub-page within the www.dmi.dk domain. This will ensure that project stakeholders can still find information about the project even after its activities and funding have finished, as well as facilitate collaboration with new projects or initiatives that start towards, or just after, the end of ObsSea4Clim.

7 Data privacy and ethics

ObsSea4Clim is committed to maintaining the highest standards of data privacy and ethics. Key information on data handling in compliance with GDPR is reported in Deliverable D7.1 "OEI – Requirement No.1" and will therefore not be repeated in this current deliverable.